

CARAS-R

Name and Surname:

Grade/Course:

INSTRUCTIONS

- Look at the following row of faces. One face is different from the other two. The different face is marked.

Can you see why the middle face is marked? The mouth is the different part.

- Now look at another row of faces. Identify which one is different from the other two (without making any mark).

That's right — it is the face on the right, because the direction of the hair is different from the other two.

Below you will find similar sets of drawings to get used to the test format.

Cejas			Pelo
Boca			Ojos
Pelo			Boca

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Remember: mark with a cross (X) the face that is different from the other two in each group of three faces. You have 3 minutes.

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SCORING: Mark (A) for a correct answer and (E) for an error. Count and transfer the results.

	PD	PT
A		
E		
A-E		
ICI		